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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Percepción profesional de los especialistas en trabajo social en la prestación de servicios sociales y psicológicos a poblaciones vulnerables

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Resumen

Este artículo examina las características de la percepción profesional de los especialistas en trabajo social en la prestación de servicios sociales y psicológicos a categorías de población vulnerables. La cuestión se aborda utilizando métodos empíricos y estadísticos para evaluar la percepción socioprofesional de estudiantes y especialistas. El objetivo del estudio es realizar un análisis estructural del desarrollo del potencial personal en los futuros especialistas y en los que trabajan actualmente. Los sujetos del estudio fueron estudiantes de la facultad de pedagogía, maestros de escuela y especialistas en protección social. Por primera vez, se ha considerado la cuestión de la formación de especialistas en trabajo social a nivel de formación y reciclaje. Los resultados obtenidos sirvieron de base para la elaboración de normas profesionales para los trabajadores sociales.

Palabras clave: percepción socioprofesional, desarrollo del potencial personal, especialistas en trabajo social, estudiantes de la facultad de pedagogía, profesores de escuela, análisis estructural.

Abstract

Professional perception of social work specialists in the provision of social and psychological services to vulnerable populations

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This article examines the features of professional perception by social work specialists in providing social and psychological services to vulnerable population categories. The issue is addressed using empirical and statistical methods for assessing social-professional perception by students and specialists. The aim of the study is to conduct a structural analysis of the development of personal potential in future and currently working specialists. The subjects of the study were students of the pedagogical faculty, school teachers, and social protection specialists. For the first time, the issue of training social work specialists has been considered at the level of training and retraining. The results obtained provided a basis for the development of professional standards for social workers.

Keywords: social-professional perception, development of personal potential, social work specialists, students of the pedagogical faculty, school teachers, structural analysis.

1. Introduction

In the context of globalization of education, the transition to digitalization processes, and the educational focus on sustainable development, major attention in higher education is directly given to the problem of training for the professional activities of future specialists. Recently, the strategy of higher academic education, training, and retraining of personnel poses challenges for every higher education institution specializing in primary and additional specializations, in studying the assessment of societal needs and demands, and recognizing the importance of professionally significant personal data of a specialist, their individual features, level of communication, professional interests, and emotional-volitional sphere.

In this regard, socio-psychological issues are raised, focusing attention on aspects that characterize the personal potential of a social work specialist in their professional activities. It is necessary to say that in the conditions of the Kyrgyz Republic, social work specialists aim to define the concept of "social-professional perception" as a perception in assessing attention to the study of the personal potential of future social work specialists.

2. Literature review

Professional perception, as a psychological concept, appeared relatively recently. A synonymous concept with "perception" is "apprehension". In a historical context, human perception was first considered by the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle as the sensation of sensory perception in the process of cognition (Ebbesen et al., 2022) Later, comparing perception with understanding the act of cognition and its connection with other mental cognitive processes and human thinking, G.W. Leibniz considered perception as a state of unclear consciousness, gradually transitioning under the influence of attention into a state of clear and meaningful consciousness (Leibniz, 1951).

Considering the problem of perception in the key definition of the psychological concept, the history of psychology has devoted a considerable period of time to the study

of perception as one of the types of mental cognitive processes, establishing a scientific evidential basis for the physiology of human psyche, and defining the properties and types of perception.

Throughout different historical periods of psychological research, perception has been understood differently, and it has had a broad scientific range of understanding and interpretation. In this direction, the works of scholars from various psychological schools and directions are dedicated, including M. Wertheimer, J. Bruner, N. Wiener, W. Wundt, J.J. Gibson, W. Köhler, K. Koffka, D. Marr, I.P. Pavlov, J. Piaget, E. Titchener, A.I. Kovalev, and others.

Certain significance to the understanding of perception is also noted in the works of Immanuel Kant. According to Kant, perception as an inner sense is "the sense through which the soul contemplates itself or its inner state" (Kant, 1970, p. 93). The word "or" here indicates that Kant, apparently, considers that the inner sense is capable of contemplating itself both as "I" and the mental states of a person (Kant, 1786, p. 30).

Highlighting the development of psychoanalytic theory on the nature of consciousness and the unconscious, Carl Gustav Jung considers archetypes as a form of perception and understanding of reality. The author describes the "persona" as our conscious personality, which represents our identity and our conscious motives, that is, the social role a person plays in meeting the demands made on them by society, the public face of the personality perceived by others, hiding vulnerable and painful spots, weaknesses, flaws, intimate details, and sometimes the essence of a person's character. Jung's "persona" is an archetype representing the mask and role we adopt in social life. The persona is the official face of the personality. It represents the mask of the collective psyche. It is a compromise between the individual and sociality. The persona acts as a secondary reality, purely a compromise formation, in which others sometimes see much more than the individual himself. The persona is a facade, a two-dimensional reality, a balanced result of the interaction of an individual's Person archetypes and the people interacting with them (Ebbesen et al., 2022, p. 154).

Such an approach in understanding justifies the perception in the socio-psychological conditioning of a personality's social and individual positions as a persona. In the mid-20th century, perception as a scientific problem of holistic reflection of the world and internal contemplation of the human world becomes the definition of the concept of "social perception," introduced by the American psychologist, a Harvard University Ph.D., Jerome Bruner. In his works, he proved that perception is generated not only by sensations but also by reason.

The introduced concept of social perception (the perception of one person by another) became a new direction of scientific-psychological research in the second half of the 20th century, addressing the person as both an object and subject of social interaction. This led to a rethinking of the paradigmatic foundations of psychological science in the field of studying perception. A deeper scientific disclosure of the regularities of the process of human perception by another person (understanding another person) and the role of this process in human relationships is associated with

the name of the scientist A.A. Bodalev. In his understanding, perception is "the cognition and mutual influence of people on each other - an essential element of any joint activity, even if its purpose is not directly to solve educational tasks, and it is entirely aimed at achieving some material result. How people reflect and interpret each other's appearance and behavior and assess each other's capabilities largely determines the nature of their interaction and the results they achieve in joint activities (Bodalev, 2015, p. 9).

In such a definition, it is necessary to consider the aspect of understanding that joint activity implies the nature of professional activity and the specifics of the profession in which a person is involved and with whom they interact. Today, the classical understanding of perception is a cognitive (mental) process, the result of which is the formation of a subjective world picture through the direct impact of an object or phenomenon on human senses. The ability to perceive the surroundings is one of the important properties of our psyche (Ingold, 2021).

Noting the retrospective view, it is interesting that professional perception as a psychological concept initially originated in social psychology and is now comparable to the concept of social perception. Social perception is a process that arises during the interaction of people with each other and includes the perception, study, understanding, and evaluation of social objects by people: other people, themselves, groups, or social communities. It is determined that the process of social perception is a complex and branched system of forming images of social objects in a person's consciousness as a result of such methods of people's understanding of each other as perception, cognition, understanding, and study. The term "perception," more restrictively explaining that "it contemplates the image of the psyche internally," and does not define the formation of an observer's representation of their interlocutor, as this is a more specific process with a completely different psychological basis. Perception is a theoretical concept characterizing an artificially isolated fragment of the whole process of cognition and subjective interpretation of the world by a person. Social perception is a complex, multi-component concept, attempting to explain the unique phenomenon of people's understanding of each other as a whole. The concept of "social perception" includes everything that is conventionally designated by various terms and studied separately: the actual process of observing behavior; the interpretation of perceived behavior in terms of the reasons for the behavior and expected consequences; emotional evaluation; and the construction of one's own behavioral strategy (Snyder et al., 1977).

The concept emerged as a necessity for a new mental, social, and cultural reality, understanding interpersonal communication and interaction, the importance of external manifestations (appearance, behavior, speech) and the internal perception of oneself (Bandura, 2006).

A.L. Fatykhova and A.S. Lisina considered the social-perceptual competence of a teacher as an essential prerequisite for purposeful activity, which allows them to perform their professional duties using existing experience, knowledge, personal qualities, and also to adapt their activities in various situations as a stable characteristic of personality,

including the following components: motivational, cognitive, emotional, and operational-activity (Fatykhova et al., 2017).

In this article, we explore social-professional perception in terms of not only its role and significance but also its meaningful content in studying the nature of professional activity. Living in a profession, life within a profession, occupies every specialist, with a life orientation towards the new, changing, and stable development in the profession.

A vivid example was the scientist V.V. Solozhenkin, who in his work raised issues about the psychological basis of the activity of future doctors, defining the "persona of the doctor" proposed a structural pedagogical model, in which he showed how primary representations, self-awareness skills, and group consolidation are formed, where students learn about the functioning of individual spheres of human psyche in norm (Kolominsky, 1986). This allowed the scientist to help students "acclimate" to the profession of a doctor, to feel a sense of the profession, to love it, understand their role, believe in their professional achievements, be resilient and dedicated to the profession, and not to lose its appeal. Demanding resilience and firmness from his proteges, the scientist himself treated his students with tender care.

The interpretable attitude of the scientist towards his professional activity clearly delineated his professional position in feelings and faith, consciousness and thinking, attitude and worldview. There are many such examples among psychologists - professionals, when we talk about schools of well-known scientists. For Kyrgyzstan, these names are associated, first of all, with the names of psychologists such as N.N. Palagina, A.A. Brudny, E.S. Orozaliev, A.A. Chazova, Ch.A. Shakeeva, T.A. Konurbaeva, D.M. London, and others.

The problem of educating a person by a person, as noted by A.A. Rean (Rean, 1999; 2002), Y.L. Kolominskiy (Kolominsky, 1986) has become extremely popular in world psychology over the last 30-35 years. Many works dedicated to it have been published in our country and abroad (Kuzmina, 1999, p. 232).

One of the most important mechanisms of interpersonal cognition is stereotyping. Under the influence of others and due to interaction with them, each person forms more or less concrete standards, using which, they assess other people. Regardless of whether a person is aware of it or not, they always perceive those around them through the prism of existing stereotypes (Rean, 2002).

Our research concentrated on the aspects of pedagogical professional perception. The objective was to explore how prospective teachers (namely, students) view the character traits of a primary school teacher and the self-perception held by primary school teachers.

3. Methods and Materials

To address the central research question, the study employed a pedagogical strategy known as the "cluster strategy" from the pedagogical technology framework "Developing

Critical Thinking through Reading and Writing" (Still et al., 1988, pp. 66-70). This strategy, which supports non-linear and unrestricted thought, facilitates free and open thinking on a given topic.

Participants included future primary school teachers in their fifth year of education, recent graduates, and practicing primary school teachers, amounting to a total of 30 individuals. Participants were instructed to place the term "primary school teacher" at the center of a sheet of paper and freely associate words and ideas that they connect with this role. They were then asked to articulate as many related concepts as occurred to them and, subsequently, to formulate their personal definitions of a "primary school teacher."

The study's analysis was grounded in the theory of reflexive-perceptual abilities as detailed by Y.L. Kolominskiy (Kolominsky, 1986) and N.V. Kuzmina (Kuzmina, 1999). These abilities pertain to how individuals interpret the dynamics of subject-object relationships within educational environments and relate to the teacher's sensitivity to both their own persona and that of their colleagues. The efficacy of a teacher's self-awareness and comprehension of others' personalities, especially prospective teachers, is therefore posited to hinge on these faculties.

Following the data collection, a comparative analysis of responses was conducted to discern patterns and draw insights regarding the professional perception among educators at various stages in their careers.

4. Results and Discussion

The Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of the collected data, which provides an evaluative perspective on the pedagogical professional perception among future and current primary school teachers. This analysis is instrumental in understanding the dynamics of self-perception and the perceived identity of a primary school teacher within the educational profession.

Table 1
Results of the Data on Associations Obtained

Self-Perception		Perception of others	
<p>The teacher's personality is a source of light, around which rays spread into the darkness.</p> <p>The teacher's personality is the builder of the 'tower' of knowledge and success.</p>	<p>The teacher's personality is the 'face' of society.</p>	<p>I see the teacher's personality, first and foremost, as a highly moral member of society, honest, open, conscious, capable of creative thinking and 'advancing' the thoughts of children.</p>	<p>The teacher's personality is primarily a flexible individual who can apply their knowledge and skills not only in the field of educational activities but also in other areas: in business, medicine, construction, communications, etc., should have at least a second specialty and know at least 1-2 foreign languages.</p>
Degree of Attractiveness		Degree of Unattractiveness	
<p>The teacher's personality is the 'divine' beginning of a growing 'human being,' you could say, the spiritual side that determines the child's further life potential.</p>	<p>The teacher's personality is the 'measure' of a child's external and internal life, maintaining the degree of balance in the child's life.</p>	<p>The teacher's personality should be focused on the process of a child's development and the outcome of their activities, not on attending lessons, frequency of responses in class, or their own subjective preparation.</p>	<p>In the classroom, it should not be the teacher working, but the children, who, I assure you, are capable of taking responsibility for learning. In the classroom, we often see the opposite.</p> <p>Disappointment in the profession.</p>

As noted by A.A. Rean and Y.L. Kolominsky, "The reflexive-perceptive skills of a teacher form a limited complex: to recognize one's own individual-psychological characteristics, to assess one's psychological state, and to carry out a multifaceted perception and adequate understanding of the student's personality. Like any skills in general, they are based on a system of corresponding knowledge (laws and mechanisms of interpersonal cognition and reflection, age psychology of children, adolescents, youth) and certain skills. No matter how extensive and varied the mentioned knowledge might be, without the presence of a complete complex of corresponding skills, reflexive-

perceptive abilities cannot be formed. The complex of so-called reflexive-perceptive skills allows a teacher to perform some actions related to the cognition of a student's personality without conscious element-by-element regulation and control. In our view, the structure of these skills includes three types - socio-perceptive, reflexive, and intellectual. The latter presuppose the automatization of methods for solving individual pedagogical tasks on self-knowledge and cognition of students' personalities" (Solozhenkin, 1997, p. 321).

The above fully applies to the objectives of our study, where we tried to explore the features of perceptual activity in the profession of primary school teachers among future primary school teachers, as well as among real teachers who have been working in the field of professional activity for several years.

Overall, as our research has shown, in compiling the cluster, both students and teachers formed associations in four groups of directions: self-perception, perception of others, degrees of attractiveness, and unattractiveness.

All associations related to the key concept of "teacher personality" in both groups of respondents are somewhat similar to each other and in some cases very different.

For the groups of associations related to "self-perception" and "degree of unattractiveness," both groups of respondents have developed a significant number of associations, while for the groups "self-perception" and "relationships of others," significantly fewer associations were identified. In our view, this is because the first two groups of associations touch more on personally significant emotional aspects, whereas the latter concern the business side of professional activity.

An interesting direction for further work could be to explore our study by raising questions about the professional training of a future specialist - a practical psychologist and the functioning of psychological services in various organizations.

The recognition of the importance of psychological knowledge for practice in education and training in higher education is determined by the emergence of increased public interest in psychological help. Understanding that there is an objective necessity and pressing need for psychological knowledge in the educational system, recognizing and accepting the fact that conceptual views have the potential to solve problems in the process of education and training in higher education institutions becomes logical and justified.

5. Conclusion

Thus, from the retrospective analysis of the definition of the psychological concept, three moments can be highlighted:

- Perception was considered as a psychological cognitive process, experiencing of senses, living through these feelings;

- Perception as the perception of people by each other, the social component in interacting with each other, interpersonal relationships, considered as social perception;
- Perception as self-relationship in one's profession.

Considering the trends of the educational paradigm within the competency-based approach and the humanization of modern education, professional perception acts as a phenomenon of perceiving a profession in education, in assessing the needs for choosing a future profession, personally significant characteristics, and value-meaningful relationships to the profession.

Looking at the problem of the concept of forming and developing the personal potential of the subject in education, the future specialist, professional perception becomes an active way of knowing one's future profession, allowing to perceive its attractiveness, demand, and dedication to one's work, emotional comfort from the usefulness of one's labor, and internal resilience to one's professional business.

It is also significant that well-developed personal-professional qualities have the opportunity to develop and act as a relevant component of regulation of actions and deeds in professional activity (Chazova, 1999).

Professional perception is nothing else but living one's future profession, a holistic subjective reflection of the real situation in achieving success, showing professional interest, defining personal-professional qualities and values, motivation, communication, interaction, professional reflection, and reflection of professional mastery and experience.

It can be said that such professional perception as a psychological concept is more inherent in understanding the stability of processes of formation and development of professional activity of future specialists.

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